

DEMONSTRATING TECHNOLOGIES TO PRODUCE LIQUID RENEWABLE ENERGY CARRIERS FROM CARBON EMISSIONS CAPTURED FROM ENERGY INTENSIVE INDUSTRIES

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ABSTRACT: Energy intensive industries (EIIs) face a major challenge of remaining competitive while taking steps to drastically reduce their carbon emissions, in line with the ambitious climate policies being established in EU and the pressing environmental concerns worldwide. In this context, carbon capture and utilization (CCU) technologies powered by renewable energy sources (RES) will play a key role to prevent further carbon release into the atmosphere while obtaining valuable products from it, such as renewable energy carriers (RECs). The EU-funded CAPTUS project aims at making EII-derived CO₂ an exploitable resource for valuable products through the demonstration of three efficient and viable CCU technologies at TRL7, where the CO₂ captured from cement, steel and chemical plants will be valorised into different RECs. All the CAPTUS processes involve an integration of surplus renewable energy, ultimately contributing to heightened efficiency and a more sustainable transition, as well as detailed analyses on safety, environmental, societal, and business aspects.

Keywords: carbon capture and utilization, energy intensive industries, hydrothermal liquefaction, bio-oil, TAGs, formic acid

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2019, energy-intensive industries (EIIs) accounted for 17% of the European Union's greenhouse gas emissions, underscoring the critical role of their decarbonization in achieving climate neutrality. Policies have been evolving to address this issue, e.g. the Industrial Plan under the Green Deal (February 2023), which acknowledges the imperative of modernizing and decarbonizing energy-intensive industries, and the Net Zero Industry Act (March 2023), which strives to accelerate the production of clean technologies within the EU [1]. In the face of said global challenges, posed by climate change and the imperative to transition towards a sustainable energy future, the CAPTUS project (Demonstrating energy intensive industry-integrated solutions to produce liquid renewable energy carriers from captured carbon emissions) emerges to push forward innovation and progress in the field of carbon capture and utilization (CCU) technologies. The ambitious undertaking of this innovation action project is strategically designed to demonstrate sustainable and cost-effective pathways to produce high-value Renewable Energy Carriers (RECs) from the CO₂ emitted from hard to decarbonize EIIs.

In this context, the main objective of the CAPTUS project is to showcase innovative solutions that leverage the valorization of industrial carbon emissions with the integration of surplus renewable electricity. By doing so, the project aims to address the pressing need for decarbonization and the development of economically viable pathways to produce RECs in three distinct demonstration sites, each representative of a different energy intensive industry, namely: a steel plant, a chemical plant, and a cement plant.

The CAPTUS project is characterized by its multifaceted approach, encompassing three unique value chains (see Figure 1). These value chains will be further detailed in the next section.

- CO₂-derived TAGs: Bioprocess in a Steel Plant
- CO₂-derived bio-oils: Microalgae Cultivation and Hydrothermal Liquefaction (HTL) in a Chemical Plant
- CO₂-derived formic acid: Electrochemical Reduction in a Cement Plant

Figure 1: Overview of the three EIIs and respective technologies and processes addressed in CAPTUS

This work will delve into the main objectives of the CAPTUS project, emphasizing the importance of developing and implementing innovative solutions at Technology Readiness Level 7 (TRL7) in the three demonstration sites. Safety, environmental considerations, societal impacts, and business aspects are given due diligence in the comprehensive evaluation of the proposed solutions. Furthermore, the full replication potential of these solutions will be highlighted through a thorough cost-benefit analysis in three additional replicators.

The last section of the paper (Section 3) presents further details of the HTL process to convert microalgae into an energy-dense bio-oil, a process in which CIRCE

is actively working to develop a robust operation procedure, as well as find optimal conditions to maximize bio-oil yield.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE CAPTUS DEMO SITES

2.1 Two-stage microbiological fermentation from the flue gas-derived CO₂ of a steel plant into TAGs

A complete CCU process will be demonstrated by means of an innovative technology based on a multi-stage fermentation process. A gas fermentation process to convert CO₂-rich steel PSA tail gas into acetate will be developed, optimized and demonstrated at the steelmaking plant. A subsequent liquid fermentation process to convert acetic acid (intermediate) into medium and long chain triglycerides (TAGs) will be developed and validated at pilot scale in real industrial conditions, in-line with the primary gas fermentation process. Downstream Processing (DSP) will be performed in a relevant environment simulating real industrial conditions (TRL 7). This combined carbon capture and bioconversion process comprises four steps:

- Stage 1 (gas capture and separation): collection of the industrial steel-mill gases (blast furnace gases, BFG) for utilization as chemical feedstock for the gas fermentation processes. This will be carried out at an existing full-scale PSA (pressure swing adsorption) system installed at the steelmaking plant and used to separate the BFG stream into a CO-rich (>30%, used in another gas fermentation process that produces ethanol) and a CO₂-rich side stream. The PSA operation will be optimized towards achieving the maximum CO₂ concentration in the PSA tail gas.
- Stage 2 (gas-substrate fermentation): primary conversion of the captured CO₂ in the PSA tail gas via gas-substrate fermentation using wild type anaerobic acetogenic bacteria to produce acetate as a chemical building block (i.e., with commercial added value as a chemical intermediate or even as an end-product). The CO₂/H₂ ratio will be optimized by means of additional “green” H₂ supply via electrolysis. The remaining CO will also be used for cell growth and conversion to acetate. The acetogenesis phase will first be characterized using bench scale gas fermenters (up to 10 L) to finetune the reactor conditions towards maximization of biomass generation and specific acetate productivity. Off-gas composition and yields of each gaseous substrate will be determined. The process will then be scaled and demonstrated on-site using a state-of-the-art, containerized mobile gas fermentation demo reactor, which will include a gas recycling (closed loop) system to target full carbon usage. As such, the gas fermentation process will be demonstrated at TRL 7.
- Stage 3 (liquid-substrate fermentation): secondary bioconversion to produce valuable products (TAGs) using crude bio-acetate as substrate. Strains of the selected aerobic yeast will be engineered, and synthetic biology tools will be used in this step. The objective of strain engineering and process optimization is to maximize lipid titer, productivity and overall yield. After the validation of the optimal operation of the novel two-stage fermentation process, the directly coupled, integrated biological process will be scaled up and demonstrated at TRL7.
- Stage 4: Downstream processing for isolation of the TAGs. The DSP process will consist of 1) mechanical

cell disruption (heat shock, steam explosion, or bead milling), 2) centrifugation and/or microfiltration, 3) water removal (oil-in-water emulsion breaking) and 4) dead-end filtration. The TAGs obtained will be characterized to define a product roadmap.

2.2 Photosynthetic fixation of flue gas-derived CO₂ from a chemical plant into microalgae and hydrothermal liquefaction into bio-oil

A complete CCU process will be demonstrated by means of an innovative technology based on microalgae cultivation in tailored design photobioreactors (PBRs) followed by hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL). The whole value chain to convert the CO₂ flue gas coming from a chemical plant into high energy content bio-oils will be developed, optimized and demonstrated at the demo site under real industrial conditions. This combined CCU process comprises three stages:

- Stage 1 (flue gas conditioning). This CAPTUS solution focuses on energy-efficient removal of unwanted gases (e.g., N₂, O₂) instead of adsorption concentration. This innovative process involves a two-column gas cleaning stage and active carbon purification as a first step, N₂ removal and O₂ elimination through membrane filtering, resulting in purified CO₂ (>95%) in a second step. In a third step, the purified CO₂ is liquefied.
- Stage 2 (microalgae cultivation). The CCU process integrates CO₂ capture with microalgae cultivation in closed PBRs, designed to optimize CO₂ dissolution and enhance overall efficiency. The unit will demonstrate a replicable environmental solution, combining chemical industry effluents with algal production, emphasizing closed systems for higher biomass productivity. The entire capture and cultivation unit will be installed as an integrative environmental solution for flue gas processing, originating biomass (algae) that will be fed to the HTL stage.
- Stage 3 (hydrothermal liquefaction). Closing the CCU loop, stage 3 focuses on hydrothermal liquefaction to valorize microalgae. The HTL process promotes thermal degradation of lipid-rich microalgae under moderate temperatures and high pressures, facilitating the production of high-energy bio-oils [2]. The HTL development addresses challenges such as operating pressures and feedstock impurities, aiming to increase bio-oil yields and reduce processing time and costs, thus establishing optimal reaction conditions for bio-oils production. Furthermore, the bio-oil quality will be assessed to find its optimal properties for the latter downstream biofuel upgrading.

2.3 Electrochemical reduction of flue-gas derived CO₂ from a cement plant into formic acid

The third CO₂ valorization pilot will produce formic acid/formate, being demonstrated through carbon capture and utilization coupled technologies for an efficient and selective electrochemical conversion of CO₂ in continuous operation mode. An advanced electrode/reactor configuration to convert the almost pure CO₂ stream (ca. 98%) derived from a Continuous Swing Adsorption Reactor (CSAR) unit will be developed, optimized and demonstrated at a cement plant in TRL 7. This combined carbon capture-electrochemical conversion process comprises 2 steps:

- Stage 1 (flue gas conditioning). The flue gas stream generated at the cement plant will be used as the input of the CSAR mobile unit [3]. This step will focus on

adapting and optimizing the CSAR adsorption technology to manage flue gases and integrating it with the CO₂ conversion technology for formic acid production. The main goal is to implement the best strategies for capture and utilization integration.

• Stage 2 (electrochemical reduction). The technology for producing formic acid/formate through CO₂ electrochemical reduction has been successfully demonstrated in laboratory conditions under continuous operation [4]. The performance of the current reactor design will be optimized in a larger prototype based on an advanced electrode/reactor configuration that maximizes the reaction selectivity and productivity towards formic acid/formate. CFD simulations, drawing on experience from simulating water and aluminum electrolyzers, will focus on better understanding the multiphase hydrodynamic behavior inside the reactor, identifying mechanisms that limit the performance and proposing pathways for improving the continuous operation. Hence, Multiphysics models will be used in CAPTUS to support the scale-up of the technology from lab- to pilot-scale. This demo-site will cover the study of the effect of flue-gas on the behavior of CO₂ reduction, and the integration of all the necessary steps to transform CO₂ into formic acid/formate. While the focus of the current technology is the production of formic acid, the advances expected will ultimately evaluate the potential of expanding this technology to produce other low-carbon chemicals.

The three demo-sites of the CAPTUS project are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Description of the demo sites under development in the CAPTUS project

The next section will detail the microalgae HTL process in the context of the CAPTUS project. This is a step led by CIRCE which recently started.

3 EXPERIMENTAL DESCRIPTION OF DEMO 2 – THE HTL PROCESS

The hydrothermal liquefaction process will be performed at CIRCE's facilities, in a 3-liter reactor (Figure 3) able to withstand 300 bar and 420 °C. This process represents a cutting-edge technology to convert wet biomass streams into high-energy bio-oils. Subjecting the feedstock to high pressures and temperatures in the presence of water, leads to the breakdown of the organic matter and the formation of the liquid products. HTL is a versatile end efficient method for converting a wide range of biomass feedstocks into valuable energy-dense streams and chemical building blocks.

Figure 3. The hydrothermal liquefaction reactor (3L capacity)

The principle of HTL revolves around replicating the natural geological processes that transform organic matter into fossil fuels over geological timescales. By subjecting biomass to elevated temperatures (typically between 200-400°C) and pressures (50-250 bar) in an aqueous environment, HTL accelerates the thermochemical degradation of the organic polymers, lipids, and carbohydrates present in the biomass. Water acts as both a solvent and a reactant, facilitating the breakdown of complex organic molecules into simpler molecules. The ability to process feedstocks with very high-water contents is one of the main advantages of this technology, as the usual energy-intensive drying pretreatments are thus avoided. [5] HTL has been extensively demonstrated in literature to upgrade wet sludges, wet biomasses, and microalgae streams, showcasing the potential of this technology [6].

Even though integrating CO₂ capture and the HTL process using microalgae presents a significant opportunity, substantial challenges need to be tackled to advance with the technology maturity and cost-competitiveness. Economically processing microalgae into a feasible and sustainable liquid biofuel, which is a low-cost, renewable produced item, is a complex task. In this sense, an optimization stage is needed to maximize the production of algae, bio-oils and their further extraction and possible upgrading. The work performed by CIRCE in this demo is going to be focused on the maximization of the oil yield through the optimization of the HTL operational conditions and of the purification process. In this regard, the design of experiments considers three different variables of study: temperature, algae concentration and residence time, and oil yield as response variable. The set of selected conditions are shown in Table . The algae selected for its processing in the project will be *Tetraselmis* sp., due to its high energy content. The composition of a typical *Tetraselmis* sp. (dry form) is shown in Table .

Table I: Operation conditions for oil yield maximization

Variable	Value 1	Value 2	Value 3
Temperature (°C)	280	315	350
Algae concentration (wt%)	10	20	30
Residence time (min)	30	60	90

Table II: Typical biochemical composition of a commercially available microalgae *Tetraselmis* sp. (dry form)

Variable	Unit	Value
Proteins	g/100g	20-30
Lipids	g/100g	7-13
Carbohydrates	g/100g	8-15
Fibers	g/100g	9-20
Ash	g/100g	25-40
Moisture	g/100g	9-12

The combination of all the shown variables will result in a set of 27 experiments, that will be performed twice for the sake of reproducibility. Once this first set is finished and the optimal conditions are selected, other variables will be introduced into the study, such as the effect of the initial pressure, use of inexpensive homogeneous catalysts such as salts, water phase reuse, among others.

It is also worth noting that the purification process needs to be optimized too. The current procedure, depicted in Figure 4, shows an intensive use on organic solvents, such as ethyl acetate, and several separation and purification steps. These multiple steps arise as a solution to the combination of products obtained throughout the reaction, which are: a mixture of solids (ashes and carbon rich solids, i.e. hydrochar) and liquids (aqueous phase and organic phase). Most of the desired oil can be found impregnated in the solids, so the stirring and washing operation is crucial to recover the produced oils. Then, solids need to be dried. Parallely, a liquid-liquid extraction needs to be performed to recover mid-polarity organics that end up dissolved in the aqueous phase. Finally, the two combined organic phases (from the solids washing and from the L-L extraction step) need to be evaporated to obtain a high purity oil. This first procedure version aims at recovering as much organic product as possible and the organic solvent was chosen based on SSbD (safe and sustainable by design) principles: ethyl acetate can be easily recovered and reused by distillation, has an adequate polarity considering the microalgae products, and is considered to have a low environmental impact. Furthermore, it is much safer than solvents typically used in L-L extraction, such as DCM (dichloromethane).

Figure 4. Hydrothermal liquefaction post-processing steps

The above operations clearly pose a challenge for upscaling, as a large-scale process would be energy intensive (especially for evaporation steps) and solvent demanding. Energy integration and solvent recovery need to be included as future steps in order to find a viable solution that will increase the sustainability and feasibility of the whole value chain. Furthermore, an industrial operation of this process would be ideally

implemented in (semi)continuous mode due to the overall lower costs, higher production rates and lower downtimes. For this reason, CAPTUS has tasks devoted to the modelling and simulation of the HTL process, which will enable a techno-economic analysis of industrially suitable systems able to operate continuously. The initial strategy for the simulation activities will be to selection of the governing equations that will be used to develop the CFD models of the key equipment selected from the different DEMO sites. The development of reduced-order models (ROMs) for each technology will be carried out to allow the CFD models to be integrated in DWSIM a process simulation software. These models will incorporate experimental data and theoretical equations to simulate the performance of integrated systems realistically.

Finally, the composition of the different outputs from the HTL process will be analysed in order to explore their possible uses. For example, characterization and upgrading of the bio-oils to biofuels is considered in the CAPTUS scope, and nutrient recovery (from the aqueous phase), soil amenders (from the solid product), among other products can be envisioned for the other generated streams in order to reach full circularity.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The EU-funded CAPTUS project aims at converting the CO₂ emitted by energy intensive industries into an exploitable resource for valuable products through the demonstration of three efficient and viable CCU technologies at TRL7. The CO₂ captured from cement, steel and chemical plants will be valorized into different renewable energy carriers with a focus on the integration of renewable energy sources. In the framework of CAPTUS, CIRCE actively participates as project's coordinator and in the simulation and experimental development of a process to convert microalgae into energy-dense bio-oils via hydrothermal liquefaction in liter-scale (within the second demonstrator).

The anticipated results of CAPTUS extend beyond technological advancements. For instance, the project aims to advance the European scientific basis, enhance technology competitiveness, and de-risk renewable energy carrier value chains through practical demonstrations at relevant, industrially sound scales. Sustainability is a key focal point, with an emphasis on improving techno-economic efficiency and replication possibilities, reducing CO₂/GHG emissions, and mitigating renewable electricity economic or curtailment losses — all supported by a robust life cycle assessment and considerations on safety, socio-environmental, and business aspects.

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6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101118265. The responsibility for the information and the views set out in this document lies entirely with the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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